

IS THE ENGINEERING STUDENTS' SELF-ASSESSMENT ACCURATE? ANALYSING MIDTERM TESTS IN TERMS OF SELF-ASSESSMENT ACCURACY

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ABSTRACT

There is a high drop-out rate in engineering higher education, the reasons can be grouped into four categories: economic explanations, individual pedagogical-psychological, learning-related reasons, socio-cultural influences. This paper discusses the problem of the accuracy of self-assessment among the individual pedagogical and psychological reasons.

During the maths midterm tests, students self-assessed on each task, which was compared with the points given by the teacher. More than 80% of students overestimated their actual performance in all midterms, and this overestimation was moderate. Based on the relationship between accuracy scores and test results, students who achieved better results in the midterms gave more accurate self-assessments than those who performed poorly, which confirms the Dunning-Kruger effect in engineering education. Feedback based on their performance may affect the accuracy of self-assessment. Feedback from the midterm caused a significant improvement in self-assessment for students who met mid-term requirements, while there was no such improvement for those who did not. Thus, underperforming students did not benefit enough from the feedback from the first midterm, and the accuracy of their self-assessment did not improve.

The fact that there is a significant difference in the accuracy of self-assessment between students who fulfilled mid-term requirements and those who did not. The self-assessments of the former was closer to the teacher's evaluation than those of the latter. This may be problematic because weaker students are less aware of their deficiencies due to their inaccurate self-assessment, and thus they may stop their preparation short of what is necessary, and may not ask for help when needed.

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1 INTRODUCTION

The high drop-out rate in engineering education can be reduced in several ways, one of them is a step-by-step growth supported by an instructor. Next to a personalised tutoring, self-assessment activities can be a simple way of supporting learners to organise their personal learning and to learn to self-manage their learning [1].

Self-assessment is a descriptive and evaluative act carried out by someone concerning his personal abilities, processes and products [2] which is an integral part of learning according to constructivist learning theory. It assumes that the individual learner actively builds new knowledge and skills on his current constructs (schemas), for which external environment only provide the opportunity. In order for learners to progress and move towards their personal development goals, they need feedback (formative) and assessment (normative) on their performance [3] (Fig.1).

Fig. 1. Constructivist learning model (based on [3])

Harlem and Belski's [4] research refined the constructivist learning model by showing that novice and expert engineers reflect at different stages of the learning process. Their study found that novice engineers reflect only when they make mistakes while expert engineers tend to reflect continuously when they solve problems. In addition, expert engineers reflect on both problem solving processes (planning and implementation) and personal assumptions (understanding the problem), novice engineers reflect only on processes.

Differences in self-assessment are not only observed on the basis of proficiency in a particular field, but also on the basis of competences. Self-evaluation errors of poor and top performers differ too. Based on Dunning–Kruger effect, poor performers in many social and intellectual domains appear largely unaware of their lack of competence. Their deficiencies make it doubly difficult - on the one hand, they make mistakes because of their incomplete and incorrect knowledge, and on the other hand, these same deficiencies prevent them from recognizing when they are making mistakes [5].

2 OBJECTIVE

The purpose of this short paper is to reveal accuracy of self-assessment of engineering students, some relationships between self-assessment and performance, and the impact of feedback on self-assessment. Therefore, the present study aimed to answer the following questions:

1. To what extent are engineering students overestimating and underestimating their performance in the course Mathematics 1?
2. Is there a significant interrelationship among accuracy scores and performance?
3. Is there a significant difference in the accuracy of self-assessment between students who fulfilled mid-term requirements and those who did not?
4. Does the accuracy of assessment change during the semester?

3 METHODOLOGY

3.1 Measure of self-assessment

Several indices of self-assessment can be distinguished, e.g. the accuracy (reliability) and the direction of the bias (validity). Based on the literature [6] the accuracy and direction of students' self-assessment was measured using two indicators: the realism/bias score and the accuracy score.

$$\text{Realism/bias score} = (\text{Average self-assessment score over all items in the test}) - (\text{Average performance score}^2 \text{ over all items in the test})$$

Accuracy score = the absolute value of the difference between the self-assessment score and performance score for each test item, summed over all items on a test, and divided by the total number of items

During the semester, students wrote two midterm tests and an exam. To take the exam, students must achieve a score of 50% in the two tests together. Those who did not meet this requirement could take a make-up test. Each test consisted of 6 tasks for 2 points per task. Before the test, students were given the opportunity to take a mock test and learn the scoring rules for each task. Students graded each task scoring 0, 1 or 2 points. Teacher assessment could also be 0, 1 or 2 points. Based on this, the bias value could take a value between -2 and 2, where a positive value indicates that the student overestimated his performance, while a negative value indicates underestimation. Values close to 0 indicate a lack of bias. The accuracy score could take a value between 0 and 2, where 0 indicates complete accuracy and 2 indicates complete inaccuracy.

3.2 Participants

258 engineering students took the course Mathematics1, 235 students wrote the first midterm test, 214 the second and 114 the make-up midterm test.

² Performans score is given by the teacher.

4 RESULTS

The realism and accuracy scores were calculated from the results of self-assessment following the midterm test and from the teacher’s assessment which provided the two indices to evaluate the accuracy of self-assessment. More than 80% of students overestimated their actual performance in all midterms (Table 1), and this overestimation was moderate (Fig.1).

Table 1. Distribution of realism scores

	Realism score midterm test1			Realism score midterm test2			Realism score make-up test		
	<0	0	>0	<0	0	>0	<0	0	>0
Number of students	16	18	197	29	12	166	6	8	88

Fig. 1. Realism scores in the tests

In the following, we compare the accuracy scores with the tests’ results. The results of the correlation calculation are shown in Table 2, which shows a negative correlation between the accuracy scores and the test scores. Thus, students with better results in tests have an accuracy score close to 0, i.e. they give a more accurate self-assessment of their own performance than students with weaker results. This result confirms the Dunning-Kruger effect in engineering education.

Table 2. Correlation between accuracy scores and test scores

	Accuracy score midterm test1	Accuracy score midterm test2
Midterm test1 score	-0,378**	
Midterm test2 score		-0,372**
Total score of tests	-0,312**	-0,305**

**p<0,01

The fact that there is a significant difference in the accuracy of self-assessment between students who fulfilled mid-term requirements and those who did not, adds nuance to this picture. The self-assessments of the former was closer to the teacher's evaluation than those of the latter. A similar difference is evident between those who pass the exam and those who fail. This may be problematic because weaker students are less aware of their deficiencies due to their inaccurate self-assessment, and thus they may stop their preparation short of what is necessary, and may not ask for help when needed.

Feedback based on performance (i.e. test result and mistakes made in the first midterm), and the opportunity to see the corrected test may affect the accuracy of self-assessment. Feedback from the midterm caused a significant improvement in self-assessment accuracy for students who met mid-term requirements, there was no such improvement for those who did not [Table 3]. Thus, underperforming students did not benefit enough from the feedback from the first midterm, and the accuracy of their self-assessment did not improve.

Table 3. Accuracy scores among students who met mid-term requirements and who did not

	Accuracy score midterm test1		Accuracy score midterm test2	
	Average	SD	Average	SD
Students met mid-term requirements	0,65	0,30	0,57	0,31
Students did not met mid-term requirements	0,76	0,33	0,79	0,45

5 CONCLUSIONS

Self-assessment and feedback can help the individual to make decisions on his developmental path, such as how much time and energy to invest in development, whether to seek external help, whether to continue on the path he has started. The results of the research confirmed that less talented engineering students are less aware of their deficiencies and thus have a less realistic self-image to plan their development path which can easily lead to drop-out. One of the benefits of self-assessment can come from active participation in the learning process. There are two ways to enhance participation in this way, firstly by increasing the number of self-assessment opportunities and secondly by training in self-assessment.

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